

DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH & HUMAN SERVICES
Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services
7500 Security Boulevard, Mail Stop C5-11-06
Baltimore, Maryland 21244-1850

**Office of Strategic Operations and Regulatory Affairs /Freedom of
Information Group**

Refer to: 092720197032 (SS-4772)

January 5, 2022

Ryan Jones
18422 Scottsdale Blvd.
Shaker Heights, OH 44122

ryanjonesfoia@gmail.com

Dear Mr. Jones:

This letter is in response to your Freedom of Information Act (FOIA)(5 U.S.C. § 552) request of September 27, 2019, which you submitted to the Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS), for circumcision procedures across the United States, for which Medicaid covered the costs. You requested procedure cost data from January 1, 1999. During the December 30, 2021 phone conversation and e-mail between you and Sam Seidman of my staff, you agreed to limit the scope of your request to the records received, which covers years 1999 through 2016.

After careful review of the responsive documents submitted to me, two (2) Excel spreadsheets, I am releasing these pages to you in their entirety.

Sincerely,

Jay Olin
Director, Division of FOIA Analysis - C
Freedom of Information Group

Enclosure